

WHOLE GENOME SEQUENCING AND PANGENOMIC STUDY OF MULTIDRUG-RESISTANT *STAPHYLOCOCCUS AUREUS* ISOLATES FROM PESHAWAR, PAKISTAN

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Abstract

We performed Whole-genome sequencing (WGS) of six *S. aureus* strains isolated from Peshawar, Pakistan, was conducted in this present study to identify the possible pangenome of *S. aureus*. These strains were then compared with the 200 fully sequenced genomes and 27 draft genomes of *S. aureus* from Pakistan available in the PATRIC database. Bioinformatics studies involving sequence assembly, quality check, Multi-Locus Sequence Typing (MLST), and Cluster of Orthologous Genes (COGs) were performed to examine the genetic variations and the evolutionary patterns of these strains. The de novo assembly of the *S. aureus* genomes indicated the genome size to lie between 1.6 to 2.9 Mb with average GC percentage. MLST analysis identified diverse sequence types among SA1, SA2, SA3, SA4, SA5, SA6 isolates belong to ST 45, 30, 772, 1413, 30, 30 and carries no SCCmec, (mecA gene, SCCmec type V, VII, mecA), mecA, (SCCmec type IV, mecA, Iva), (SCCmec type IV, mecA, Iva). Using the pangenome analysis of the 200 *S. aureus* genomes, it found a total of 9,118 genes while sharing 1,620 core genes, 307 soft core genes, 1,161 shell genes, and the remaining 6,030 of cloud genes. Thus, this analysis reveals the fact that the pangenome of *S. aureus* is open, suggesting its ability to obtain new genes and adapt to the environment. The COG analysis showed the functional classifications of the genes underlying metabolic processes. These outcomes are crucial for clinicians and therapeutic strategies for treating bacterial *S. aureus* infections.

Keywords: *S. aureus*, MRSA, WGS, MLST.

1. INTRODUCTION

Staphylococcus aureus (*S. aureus*) is a major pathogen, which accounts for dramatic nosocomial infections. Methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA) is one of the very organisms of nosocomial infections that pose a real danger to immunocompromised patients (1). The rate of nasal colonization of *S. aureus* to be roughly 26.01% in the community and 25.4% in healthy hospital (2).

Additionally, Bazaid et al observed that during the course of 5 years between January 2015 to December 2019 (3) found 12% of *S. aureus* in patients with urinary tract infections. Moreover, *S. aureus* was also found to be involved in a number of infections including osteoarticular infections, endocarditis, deep soft-tissue infections both in the community and hospital settings, and food poisoning (4-7).

Multidrug-resistant staphylococci may persist in the hospital environment and can neutralize drugs and biocides by biofilm formation or cell conversion in atypical forms (8). The identification of genetic factors that contribute to *S. aureus* pathogenicity and antibiotic resistance is essential for the design of treatment strategies and the prevention of the spread.

Whole genome sequencing (WGS) provides comprehensive genetic map of different organisms; allows to discover the genetic factors contributing to phenotypic distinctions, pathogenicity, as well as understanding of resistance factors (9). Due to comparative analysis of multiple *S. aureus* strains with sequenced complete genomes, the investigators become able to study the evolutionary history and the functional capabilities of the bacterium (10). This type of strategy enables the investigation of bacteria's gene plasticity and unveils not only conserved genes that are required for the organisms's sustainability but also the dispensable genes that can be acquired or lost while housing special functions and virulence attributes (11).

The concept of core and accessory genomes allows to analyze the multifaceted relationships between bacterial species and their evolution, as well as the evolution of clinically relevant phenotypes, including antibiotic resistance (12,13). Comparing the genomes of *S. aureus*, scientists can recognize how exactly populations become resistant to antibiotics and introduce targeted therapies to prevent the distribution of multidrug-resistant strains and decrease the mortality rate among affected patients.

Within the frame of this concept, exists the part of the genome that is conserved in all strains of a given species, which is known as the core genome, and the part of the genome, which differs in strain, or in groups of strains, known as the accessory genome. This concept is particularly valuable when studying the genomic potential of *S. aureus* (14). The core genome comprises of genes that are necessary for the cell metabolism and the survival of the bacteria while the dispensable genome has those genes that catalyze versatility in various conditions such as antibiotic resistance and virulence factors. (15). Pangenome analysis hence offers a paradigm for studying the genotypic and phenotypic variation and the evolutionary processes within the species.

This study therefore aimed at analyzing the genome of six *S. aureus* strains through whole genome sequencing and pangenomics. They were aligned with 200 complete genomic sequences and 27 draft genomes of *S. aureus* from Pakistan. Combining these approaches, we will be able to determine potential candidate genes and to understand the processes underlying the genotypic differences in *S. aureus*. Thus, our results have potential biological therapeutic application and much significance for the clinical prevention and treatment of *S. aureus* infection. Moreover, the improvement of clusters of orthologous groups (COGs) aided in extending the knowledge on various genes and adaptation of these strains. The present study has several significant therapeutic implications and shared several practical significances in the clinical management of *S. aureus* infections.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Bacterial isolate collection and antibiotic susceptibility testing

S. aureus isolates were taken from Khyber Teaching Hospital in Peshawar. The samples were cultured on mannitol salt agar (MSA) plates for 24 hours at 37°C. The isolates were initially identified using some of the important biochemical tests including oxidase, catalase, and coagulase assays (16). The antibiotic susceptibility for the following antibiotic classes was determined using the disc diffusion technique in accordance with CLSI 2015 guidelines: Aminoglycosides [gentamicin (10µg) and streptomycin (25µg)], macrolides [erythromycin (15µg)], clindamycin (2µg)], oxazolidinones [linezolid (30µg)], cephalosporins [cefixime (5µg) and cefepime (30µg)], carbapenems [meropenem (10µg)] (17).

2.2 DNA Extraction, quantification and whole genome sequencing

As part of the study titled " as a part of the Technical University of Denmark's (DTU) research project "Two Weeks in the World (TWIW)," The Qiagen DNeasy® Blood & Tissue kit (Qiagen, Venlo, Netherlands) was utilized for DNA extraction, and the Qubit dsDNA high sensitivity (HS) assay kit (Carlsbad, CA, USA) was utilized for quantification (18). Paired-end sequencing was used to process each sequence on an Illumina NextSeq 500 platform.

2.3 Sequence submission

The genomic sequences were uploaded with project Accession number PRJEB56918 to the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/home>) online archive.

2.4 Specie identification and sequence retrieval

The species were identified by using FIDBAC database (<http://fbac.dmicrobe.cn/>), and the raw reads FASTQ files of the isolated strains were taken from the ENA database.

2.5 Assembly and QC check

The initial stage in assembling the genome was to assess the quality of the raw sequencing data using the QUAST software (19). The genome assembler HybridSPAdes was used to assemble the raw reads together (https://github.com/kbaseapps/kb_SPAdes) (20). One bioinformatic technique that has gained a lot of attention and is used extensively is called HybridSPAdes. It is quite effective at assembling DNA sequences, especially when dealing with complex genomes.

HybridSPAdes are used efficiently for producing the de Bruijn graph with graph-based algorithms. To precisely and consistently evaluate genetic information and assemble genomic sequences, this methodology helps scientists to assemble bacterial genomes. For assembly, a number of parameters have an important role: total count of contigs, genome size, GC content, and total coverage. For predicting these parameters and assembled genome evaluation, QUAST (Quality Assessment for Genome Assembly) is used. This tool is intended to be developed for assessing the quality of assembled genomes. This tool helps researchers to provide a range of statistics like N50, L50, etc., and completeness. This led the researchers to quantitatively evaluate their assembly data. The default contig size >500 was accounted for to run the assembly.

2.6 Genome completeness identification

To confirm the completeness and annotation of the genomes, CheckM V1.0.18 (21) was utilized to run the genomes following assembly and quality check.

2.7 Genome Annotation

The structural annotation by using Prokka on the sequenced genomes was performed with default settings. To precisely annotate bacterial genomes, Prokka v1.14.5 (22) was used, and this application is designed to be efficient. Scientists investigating microbial genomes consider it an essential resource because of its exceptional speed, automation, and efficiency.

This process has a number of output file formats, such as FASTA for protein and Nucleotide and an Annotation file in GFF3 format, which would be of interest. Functional annotation was performed via using Rapid Annotation using Subsystem Technology (RAST) server (<https://rast.nmpdr.org/>) (23). By making the annotation of microbial genomes simpler, RAST's method also aids in the identification of genes, functional elements, and metabolic pathways present in DNA sequences. RAST's automated and curated approaches have been intended to boost our understanding of the genomes and biology of microorganisms.

2.8 MLST

The sequences were then subjected to MultiLocus Sequence Typing (MLST) analysis. Four isolates' contig sequences were examined using MLST Software version 2.0.9 (24). MLST helps researchers in describing genetic diversity in microorganisms, e.g., scientists

and medical professionals interested in learning about the evolution and epidemiology of microbes, this updated version provides enhanced precision and effectiveness.

The allelic profiles or STs of each strain was determined by using the Institute Pasteur technique (MLSTIP), which made use of eight housekeeping genes (*arcC*, *arcC*, *aroE*, *glpF*, *gmk*, *pta*, *tpi*, and *yqiL*) in its collection. For epidemiological studies PubMLST (25), or Public Multilocus Sequence Typing, is a potent bioinformatics approach that helps scientists evaluating genetic variants in several genes, which facilitates the tracking and understanding of the transmission pattern of infectious diseases.

PubMLST offers publicly accessible, standardized databases for MLST typing and for *SCCmec* and *spa typing* the assembled genomes subjected to Staphopia *SCCmec* (<https://github.com/staphopia/staphopiaSCCmec>) and *spaTyper* (<https://github.com/HCGBIGTP/spaTyper>).

2.9 Pangenome Analysis

The sum of all the genomes is known as the pangenome, which is the entire gene repertoire of a given species, namely the core genome and the dispensable genome. The core genome contains genes critical for the growth of the bacteria and are shared by the genomes of a certain species. While Dispensable genome, not shared by every genome and may be in charge of strain specific traits like pathogenicity, stress tolerance, and sensitivity to different stimuli. The pangenome analysis was performed for six genomes of *S. aureus* isolated strains with the dataset including 27 draft genomes from Pakistan, and 200 complete global genome sequences of *S. aureus* which were downloaded from Pathosystems Resource Integration Centre (PATRIC) (26), a comprehensive bioinformatics resource to download genomic data easily (<https://www.bvbrc.org/>).

PATRIC was identified as the efficient and most useful database to download genomic sequences on the basis of different filters like host, location, draft or complete genome at once that make it an indispensable instrument for microbiological research. The pangenome analysis on six isolates with predominantly global and local genomes was carried out using Roary version 3.13.0 (27) a pangenome pipeline. Roary reads GFF3 format and performs pangenome analysis. Roary creates three output usable formats and had one graphical output to make easy visualizations.

2.10 COG Analysis

COG database is a strong and adaptable that frequently used in biological research (28). Using this database makes it possible to analyze Clusters of Orthologous Groups (COGs) more effectively, which helps researchers identify functional traits that genes in different organisms share. The COG Bioinformatics tool makes a substantial contribution to the giving of useful insights into gene functions and evolutionary links by facilitating comparative genomics. COG analysis was performed using the Bacterial Pangenome Pipeline B-Pan. For COG, phylogenetic, and pangenome analysis, the B-Pan bacterial pangenome pipeline is used. By using COG analysis, core genes and unique genes participating in several pathways were found.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Sequence Retrieval

A total of 200 complete genome sequences of *S. aureus* were retrieved from PATRIC reported from around the world on 27th of Dec 2023. Also 27 draft genomes of *S. aureus* from Pakistan were retrieved from PATRIC database on the same date. The *S. aureus* included in the study were all reported as MDR and causing infections in human host.

3.2 Pangenome of Multi Drug Resistant *S. aureus*

Roary estimated a total of 9,118 genes in 200 *S. aureus* genomes, out of which 1620 were core genes that were conserved among 99-100% strains and which is 17.7% of total genes. 307 soft core genes were present among 95-99% strains, 1161 were shell or accessory genes that were present among 15-95% of the strains, and 6030 cloud or unique genes were present among 0-15% of the strains (**Figure 3.1**). The number of genes across genomes and their frequency, as shown in (**Figure 3.2**). The tree is compared among *S. aureus* genomes and is compared to a matrix with the core genes presence and absence (**Figure 3.3**). According to pangenome analysis, when the number of genomes increases, so do the total and unique gene counts (**Figure 3.4 & 3.5**). An open pangenome revealed that the number of *S. aureus* genomes increased along with the overall number of genes.

Figure 3.1: *S. aureus* pangenome's global strain pie chart of gene clusters displays Genes classified as core, soft core, and accessory

Figure 3.2: *S. aureus* six isolates globally based frequency graph of genome

Figure 3.3: Pang genome tree of *S. aureus* in comparison to the matrix showing the presence or absence of core and accessory genes

Figure 3.4: A graph illustrating how the overall number of genes increases as the number of *S. aureus* genomes increases

Figure 3.5: Graph shows increase in number of unique genes with increase in number of *S. aureus* Genomes which indicates diversity and adoptability of isolates

3.3 Genomic characteristics

The de novo assembly of SA1, SA2, SA3, SA4, SA5 and SA6 Illumina reads generated 18,68,47,58,38 and correspondingly, 41 contigs (>500 bp) with a GC content ranging from 32.62 to 32.76. The N50 values of SA1, SA2, SA3, SA4, SA5 and SA6 genome are <45k and L50 values are 2 to 11, respectively, and the longest contigs are between the 200k to 1000k bp in length. The genome size of SA1, SA2, SA3, SA4, SA5 and SA6 is between

1600k to 2900k bp. The number of predicted CDS are 2570, 2635, 2624, 2682, and 2547. The SA1, SA2, SA3, SA4, SA5 and SA6 harbors are 16 to 32 tRNA genes and 2 to 5 rRNA genes (**Table 3.1**).

Table 3.1: Genomic features and characteristics of MRSA strains SA1, SA2, SA3, SA4, SA5 and SA6

Genomic Characteristics						
	SA1	SA2	SA3	SA4	SA5	SA6
Genome Size(bp)	2481327	2828872	2819803	2858722	2760883	1604595
Contigs	18	68	47	58	38	41
GC content	32.76	32.72	32.68	32.62	32.69	32.69
N50	415654	82508	15303	134681	170486	136639
L50	2	11	6	7	6	6
CDs	2570	2635	2624	2682	2547	2547
Longest contig size	998731	253525	412914	292957	323688	333155
ST	45	30	772	1413	30	30
tRNA	16	27	28	27	32	24
rRNA	4	4	3	2	4	5
tmRNA	1	1	1	1	1	1

3.4 Multi Locus Sequence Typing of *S. aureus* Isolates

The Pasteur scheme, which consists of the seven housekeeping genes *arcC*, *aroE*, *glpF*, *gmk*, *pta*, *tpi*, and *yqiL*, was used to perform the MLST analysis of all 200 *S. aureus* isolates (**Table 3.2**). MLST analysis revealed 63 different sequence types among 200 strains that show high genetic diversity between *S. aureus* genomes. The most frequent sequence type was ST2 (n=240) but none of the isolated strains belong to sequence type 2. Among other STs shared by *S. aureus* isolates, the most frequently encountered were ST5 (37 isolates), ST8 (33 isolates), ST72 (12 isolates), ST9 (11 isolates), ST30 (10 isolates), and 97 STs has less than 10 isolates (**Table 3.3**). The SA1, SA2, SA3, SA4, SA5, SA6 isolate belong to ST 45, 30, 772, 1413, 30, 30 and carries no *SCCmec*, (*mecA* gene, *SCCmec* type V, VII, *mecA*), *mecA*, (*SCCmec* type IV, *mecA*, *Iva*), (*SCCmec* type IV, *mecA*, *Iva*). While belongs to variable *spa* type listed in (**Table 3.4**).

Table 3.2: *S. aureus* isolates carry sequence types and allelic profile

Strain Name	MLST (NSTs)	Multi- Locus Allelic Profile							Genome Accession
		<i>arcC</i>	<i>aroE</i>	<i>glpF</i>	<i>gmk</i>	<i>pta</i>	<i>tpi</i>	<i>yqiL</i>	
SA1	45	10	14	8	6	10	3	2	ERR10431539
SA2	30	2	2	2	2	6	3	2	ERR10431540
SA3	772	1	1	1	1	22	1	1	ERR10431542
SA4	1413	6	5	6	2	162	14	5	ERR10431545
SA5	30	2	2	2	2	6	3	2	ERR10431550
SA6	30	2	2	2	2	6	3	2	ERR10431551

Table 3.3 Multi Locus Sequence Type of selected *S. aureus*

House- Keeping Genes	Sequence types (STs)	No. of Isolates
	ST5	37
arcC genes	ST8	33
aroE	ST72	12
glpF	ST9	11
gmK	ST30	10
pta	ST45, ST15	8
tpi	ST59	6
yqiL	ST1, ST398, ST22, ST239	5
	ST228, ST152, S772, ST25	4
	ST121, ST7, ST1232, ST105, ST51, ST580	3
	ST188, ST1708, ST630, ST30, ST50	2 each
	ST6, ST88, ST12, ST9, ST20, ST87,	1 each
	ST426, ST59, ST121, ST254, ST113	

Table 3.4: Spa type of *S. aureus* isolates

Sequence name	spa Type
SA1	08-16-02-xx-34-13-17-34-16-34
SA2	07-02-16-02-16-17
SA3	t657
SA4	t314
SA5	t363
SA6	t363

3.5 COG Analysis

The COGs gene family has been discovered to be involved in different functions such as amino acid transport, small molecule transport, and morphology. For instance, with strain SA1, SA2, SA3, SA4, SA5, and SA6 (24.7%) Cluster of Orthologous Genes (COGs) for translation, (12.7%) in amino acid metabolism and transport; (10.7%) in coenzyme metabolism; (2.7%) in transcription, and (5.6) are found to be associated with energy production and conversion. There are same pattern goes for all strains but there is a slight difference when it comes to the involvement of COGs in coenzyme metabolism is higher than that of the transcription. Graphical representation of the COGs involvement in various metabolic pathways (**Figure 3.6 & 3.7**)

Figure 3.6: Circular visualization of Cluster of orthologous genes in *S. aureus* of global strains

Figure 3.7: Graph shows distribution of Cluster of orthologous genes in *S. aureus* of global strains

4. DISCUSSION

Heavy MRSA is a highly economically burdensome opportunistic multi-resistant disease that emerged due to antibiotic pressure or through MGEs such as plasmids, transposons, and prophages. Its versatile virulence traits include the ability to invade, adhere, and colonize to elude the host's immune system. Furthermore, the management of MRSA

infections is made more difficult by the emergence of novel MRSA clones (29). The virulence pattern, antibiotic resistance, and genetic epidemiology of MRSA are crucial for both prevention and treatment. Pakistani genomic data only partially document the molecular epidemiology of MRSA. It is difficult to compare the genomes of Due to the lack of research, MRSA strains in Pakistan are comparable to those in other parts of the world (30-33) have used PFGE, *SCCmec*, and MLST to characterize isolates. No study has performed whole-genome sequencing. From our vast genomic research, we have acquired a detailed understanding of the pathogenicity, resistance mechanisms, and evolutionary relationships of six strains of *S. aureus*. The identification of virulence factors, antibiotic resistance genes, prophage sequences, genomic islands, and whole-genome phylogeny paints a complete picture of these clinically significant isolates.

The WGS of six *S. aureus* isolates from Peshawar exhibited ST 45, 30, 772, 1413, 30 30 respectively. These isolates were phenotypically resistant to Tobramycin, Streptomycin, Amoxicillin, Ampicillin, Piperacillin, Penicillin, and Lincomycin. These sequence types were previously reported from Rawalpindi, Pakistan and characterization based on *SCCmec* and MLST (Syed et al. 2021).

The in silico *SCCmec* typing revealed that isolates SA2 to SA6 exhibited V, VII, IV and IVa type and all carried *mecA* gene. Therefore, possibly CA-MRSA (Baig et al. 2018; Lim et al. 2012; Wu et al. 2015) PVL can be virulence-associated gene(s) of the most CA-MRSA strains, that are generally not dependent on β -lactams and are susceptible to non- β -lactams (34-36). While on the contrary HAMRSA are taken up with the hospital and well, in the resistance of non- β -lactam antibiotics and also do not have the PVL gene (37).

In the pangenome analysis conducted with global strains set of 200 *S. aureus* genomes, 1620 were identified as core genes, accounting for 17.7% of total genes, while 307 soft core genes, 1161 were shell or accessory genes found in 15-95% of the strains, and 6030 cloud or unique genes were found in 0-15% of the strains. This depiction of *S. aureus*'s open pangenome displays the organism's ability to constantly acquire genes, emphasizing its genomic flexibility. The link between genome numbers and the development of unique genes highlights the flexibility of organisms (38).

5. CONCLUSION

This work is a great source of genetic opportunities for clinical isolates of *S. aureus* from Peshawar, which can be used to provide epidemiological information and genomic data, also as reference genomes from Pakistan. The types VII, IV and IVa in SA2 - SA6 strains are *SCCmec*, while SA1 does not possess this. The class as well as subtypes identified ST 45, 30, 772, 1413, 30 30 were responsible for the diversity among the isolates. The *S. aureus* isolates show open pangenome that reveal the continuous expansion of the *S. aureus* genome. To have a better understanding of genetic evolution and transmission patterns, more study is required on a sizable MRSA collection in Pakistan. This will improve monitoring efforts and provide useful data on public health.

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